

Industrially viable process for reduction of esters to alcohols with sodium borohydride under buffer and aqueous alcoholic conditions

Ramadas Chavakula*, M. Narayana Rao, B. Gopi Babu, K. Praveen Kumar and Ch. Srinivasa Rao

Tyche Industries Limited, H. No. C-21/A, Road No. 9, Film Nagar, Jubilee Hills, Hyderabad-500 093, India

E-mail : das.krishnac@gmail.com

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Abstract : A simple and convenient procedure for synthesis of alcohols from esters by reduction method using sodium borohydride in the presence of dipotassium hydrogen orthophosphate under aqueous alcoholic conditions is described.

Keywords : Reduction, sodium borohydride, buffer, solvent-free reaction, dipotassium hydrogen orthophosphate.

Introduction

Simple chemoselective reductions of aldehydes and ketones to the corresponding alcohols with sodium borohydride is well known¹⁻³. The reaction is normally carried out at room temperature or at reflux temperature using alcohols as solvent. Under these conditions, carboxylic acids, esters, epoxides, lactones, nitro groups, imides, amides and nitriles are not reduced. Therefore, reduction of these functional groups is carried out using stronger reducing agents like lithium aluminum hydride⁴. Sodium borohydride can, however, be easily modified to a stronger or more selective reducing agent. Some saturated acids and esters can be reduced to alcohols by combining NaBH₄ and AlCl₃ at room temperature^{5,6}. Unsaturated acids or esters formed complex compounds under these conditions. Esters have been reduced by NaBH₄ when catalyzed by LiCl (or LiI) in THF^{7,8}. Other metallic ions, such as TiCl₄⁹ and CaCl₂^{10,11} were used to enhance the reduction efficiency of NaBH₄ in various reductions.

We now report the operationally simple, highly selective and efficient preparation of alcohols from esters by reduction method using sodium borohydride in the presence of dipotassium hydrogen orthophosphate under aqueous alcoholic conditions (Scheme 1). Sodium borohydride is an inexpensive, safe to handle and environmental friendly reducing agent. This method is not only of interest from ecological point of view, but also proves to be a clean, rapid and very simple procedure.

Scheme 1

Keeping in view of above findings, we have now synthesized and characterized a series of drug intermediates (**1a-5a**, Table 1).

Experimental

¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker ADVANCE- 400 MHz, using DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent. Infrared spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer spectrum 100 FT-IR spectrophotometer. Electrospray ionization mass spectroscopy was performed using an ion trap mass spectrometer (Model 6310 agilent). Gas chromatographic analysis was performed using a Shimadzu GC-2010 Plus equipped with an Alltech poly (dimethoxysiloxane) 30 meter capillary DB-1 column.

General procedure :

Dipotassium hydrogen orthophosphate (0.04 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of isopropyl alcohol (75 ml) and purified water (25 ml) and the obtained solution was cooled to 18 °C. To this resulting mixture was added ester (0.02 mol) at 15–22 °C and the suspension was stirred at 18–22 °C for 10 min. Sodium borohydride (0.04 mol) was added portionwise over 1 h at 18–20 °C and maintained for 4 h

Table 1

Sl. no.	Substrate	Product	Time (h)	Yield (%)	Drug intermediate
1.	 1a	2	92	Cinacalcet	
2.	 2a	4	60	Mequitazine	
3.	 3a	4	87	Rupatadine	
4.	 4a	4	85	Nebivolol	
5.	 5a	6	90	Donepezil	

at RT. The completion of the reaction was monitored by GC. The reaction mass was transferred into a separating funnel and the layers were separated. Isopropyl alcohol was distilled out initially atmospherically followed by reduced pressure to reduce the traces of IPA. The resultant residue was diluted with water and then cooled to 22–30 °C. Chloroform (50 ml) was added to the reaction mass under stirring, allowed the layers to settle and separate the layers. Collected chloroform layer and distill off completely under vacuum to give corresponding alcohol.

3-(3-Trifluoromethylphenyl)propan-1-ol (1a) : Reddish oil, IR (neat) : 3350 (-OH), 2941, 2870, 1450, 1331, 1162, 1124, 1073 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 1.90 (2H, m, - CH_2), 2.08 (1H, s, -OH), 2.77 (2H, t, - CH_2), 3.67 (2H, t, - CH_2), 7.38 (2H, d, ArH), 7.45 (2H, d, ArH).

Quinuclidine-3-methanol (2a) : Yellow oil, IR (neat) : 3350 (-OH), 2941, 2870, 1450, 1331, 1162, 1124, 1073 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 1.35–1.70 (6H, m), 2.08 (1H, s, -OH), 2.15–2.40 (6H, m), 3.40–3.62 (2H, m); Mass 142.32 (M+H).

5-Methyl-3-pyridylmethanol (3a) : Yellow oil, IR (neat) : 2975 (-OH), 2881, 2835, 1589, 1455, 1376, 1164, 1030 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 2.34 (3H, s), 4.70 (2H, s), 7.55 (1H, brs), 7.26 (1H, brs), 7.29 (1H, brs), Mass 124.38 (M+H).

6-Fluoro-3,4-dihydro-2H-1-benzopyran-2-methanol (4a) : Yellow oil, IR (neat) : 3350 (-OH), 2941, 2870, 1450, 1331, 1162, 1124, 1073 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3/TMS) : δ 1.95 (2H, m), 2.28 (1H, s, -OH), 2.80 (2H, m), 3.80 (2H, m), 4.08 (1H, m), 6.77 (3H, m, ArH); Mass 183.28 (M+H).

N-Benzyl-4-hydroxymethylpiperidine (5a) : Catalytic amount of sodium hydroxide was used. Colourless oil, $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : 1.21–1.35 (2H, m), 1.42–1.56 (1H, m), 1.69 (2H, d, J 12 Hz), 1.90–2.03 (2H, m), 2.90 (2H, d, J 12 Hz), 3.46 (2H, d, J 7 Hz), 3.49 (2H, s), 7.20–7.36 (5H, m); Mass 206 (M+H).

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